

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NYAGATOMA****FIRST NAME: K. ANTOINE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK**

This page uses US English (for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting references).
The rule of style is: Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).
Used Zotero to insert references.
Used the following software: MS word 2010 on windows 7.
Note: This document is US letter ("8.5"x" format).

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without credit to the author of the source of information. Among four answers below what do you think is the example of plagiarism?**
 - Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor.¹**
 - Identify the keywords (like discuss or analyze) and clarify the approach you required to take.
 - Be sure that you understand exactly what the question requires you to do.
 - I should have a thesis statement (answer to question) and an argument).
- 2. There are different basic steps of writing essay. As a doctoral student could you tick below a right step or answer?**

¹ "ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) – EUCLID University LMS," 10, accessed June 25, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/courses/aca-401d/>.

- Identify the keywords (like discuss or analyze) and clarify the approach you required to take.
 - Be sure that you understand exactly what the question requires you to do.
 - I should have a thesis statement (answer to the question) and an argument.
 - Write an essay plan and organize your ideas.**²
3. **As a doctoral student you are expected to master types of citation. Can you identify the real type within provided answers below?**
- Electronic sources.
 - Bibliography style.**³
 - Online sources.
 - Information in citation.
4. **Which of the following is not the additional type of published sources?**
- Early English Literary works.
 - Classical.
 - Citing Newspapers in Notes.**⁴
 - Medieval.

² Ibid., 2.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

⁴ Ibid., 113.

5. **Some writers find it so difficult to write the first sentence of a report that they fall into clichés. As a student at a doctoral program you learnt that there are unavoidable statement, could you identify the right one among the following provided answers?**
- Do not repeat the language of your assignment.
 - Do not quote a dictionary definition Webster defines risk as ...
 - Do not pontificate: For centuries, philosophers have debated the burning question of.... (Good questions speak their own importance).
 - State the significance of your question.⁵**
6. **Which of the following constitutes essay writing?**
- Scope.
 - Editing.
 - Introduction, body and conclusion.⁶**
 - Referencing the essay.
7. **Which is the meaning of plagiarism within the following answers?**
- Taking someone else's words or idea.
 - It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
 - Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
 - When the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.⁷**

⁵ Ibid., 71.

⁶ “ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) – EUCLID University LMS,” 4, accessed June 25, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/courses/aca-401d/>.

8. **Case study is one of the traditions of inquiry, could you mark the right meaning of it among the following provided answers bellow?**
- Intensive description and analysis of a phenomenon, social unit, or system bounded by time or place.⁸**
 - Theory of a process, action, or interaction grounded in the views of the research participants.
 - Cultural or social group in natural setting, closely examining customs and ways of life, with the aim of describing and interpreting cultural patterns of behavior, values, and practices.
 - Investigate the meaning of the lived experience of people to identify the core essence of human experience as described by research participants.
9. **You have been taught that completing your qualitative dissertation requires different methods. Could you choose the best answer with a among the provided answers?**
- Support and give evidence for your methodological approach.
 - Provide theories related to your research question that form the development and ongoing refinement of your conceptual framework.
 - Document Review and Observation.⁹**
 - Provide support for conclusions you draw and recommendations you suggest.
10. **Reaching the final stages of writing your dissertation, it is crucial that you once again make certain necessary elements prior to it and**

⁷ Ibid., 9.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 37.

⁹ Ibid., 94.

lead to logical flow of elements or steps. With your experience as a doctoral student, can you mark or tick one of the right given answers below?

- Theoretical basis that guided the study.
- Problem statement defines subject of inquiry.**¹⁰
- Data resources that informed your study.
- Qualitative research tradition or genre.

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¹⁰ Ibid, 188.